

Synergistic Antidiabetic Effects of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Allium sativum* and SGLT2 Inhibitor Dapagliflozin in Alloxan-Induced Diabetic Rats

Shivakumar Ladde^{1*}, Jangme Diksha C², Giram Padmaja S², Patne Anamika S¹

¹Dept. of Pharmacy Practice, Channabasweshwar Pharmacy College (Degree), Latur, Maharashtra-413512, India

²Dept. of Pharmacology, Channabasweshwar Pharmacy College (Degree), Latur, Maharashtra-413512, India.

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus, particularly Type 2, is a multifactorial metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycemia and associated complications. Current therapies face limitations due to side effects and suboptimal long-term efficacy. This study investigates the synergistic antidiabetic and hypolipidemic effects of combining a hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* (garlic) with the SGLT2 inhibitor dapagliflozin in an alloxan-induced diabetic rat model. Diabetes was induced in Wistar rats through a high-fat diet and a single intraperitoneal dose of alloxan (120 mg/kg). Diabetic rats were divided into groups receiving dapagliflozin alone (5 mg/kg), or in combination with garlic extract at 200 or 400 mg/kg doses for 28 days. Fasting blood glucose (FBG), glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and serum lipid profiles were assessed. Phytochemical analysis and acute toxicity testing of the garlic extract were also performed. The combination of dapagliflozin with *A. sativum* extract produced a dose-dependent improvement in glycemic control and lipid metabolism. FBG and HbA1c levels were significantly reduced, with the 400 mg/kg garlic extract group achieving near-normal values. Additionally, lipid profiles showed a marked decrease in triglycerides and total cholesterol, alongside an increase in HDL-C levels. No signs of toxicity were observed, confirming the safety of the herbal extract. Co-administration of *Allium sativum* extract with dapagliflozin offers a synergistic therapeutic benefit, significantly enhancing glycemic control and lipid balance without adverse effects. These findings support the integration of phytotherapeutic agents with conventional antidiabetic drugs and warrant further mechanistic and clinical studies to validate the observed effects in human subjects.

Keywords: *Allium sativum*, dapagliflozin, diabetes mellitus, SGLT2 inhibitor, phytotherapy, glycemic control, lipid profile, herbal adjuvant therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic condition that is essentially distinguished by a lack of the hormone insulin, insulin resistance, or both¹, which impairs the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates². Type 1 diabetes is primarily caused by an autoimmune process that leads to the destruction of beta cells, resulting in a complete inability to produce insulin. On the other hand, type 2 diabetes is a multifactorial condition influenced by a combination of genetic, behavioural, and environmental factors³. By 2030, it's predicted that 439 million individuals worldwide would have type 2 diabetes. Due to environmental and

lifestyle risk factors, the incidence of type 2 diabetes differs significantly by geographic location³.

Type 1 diabetes is primarily an autoimmune disease, in which the immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys the insulin-producing beta cells in the pancreas⁴. Type 2 diabetes is the most prevalent, often associated with obesity and lifestyle-related risk factors^{5, 6}. In obesity, excessive accumulation of adipose tissue leads to a state of chronic inflammation and insulin resistance⁷. The excess adiposity in obese individuals results in the release of inflammatory substances such as cytokines and free fatty acids that disrupt the normal functioning of insulin signaling

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

pathways. This leads to reduced uptake of glucose by tissues, decreased insulin secretion, and impaired glucose metabolism, all of which contribute to the development of type 2 diabetes⁸⁻⁹.

SGLT2 inhibitors are a class of medications used for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. They work by inhibiting the SGLT2 transporter in the kidneys, which reduces the reabsorption of glucose and increases its excretion in the urine. This results in lower blood glucose levels and improved glycemic control in individuals with type 2 diabetes¹¹. Garlic is comprised of a variety of bioactive compounds, including alliin, diallyl sulfide, diallyl disulfide, diallyl trisulfide, ajoene, and S-allyl-cysteine. Research has demonstrated that garlic and its bioactive components possess a wide range of beneficial properties, such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, immunomodulatory, cardiovascular protective, anticancer, hepatoprotective, digestive system protective, anti-diabetic, anti-obesity, neuroprotective, and renal protective effects¹².

Despite the availability of synthetic drugs, the long-term management of diabetes remains a challenge due to side effects and limited efficacy. Thus, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the synergistic effect of *Allium sativum* (garlic) extract and dapagliflozin, an SGLT2 inhibitor, in obesity-induced

type-2 diabetic rats is a study aimed at investigating the potential benefits of using these two substances to manage diabetes in rats that have developed the condition due to obesity.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals and Extracts

- Alloxan was procured from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, United States), and dapagliflozin was obtained from HiMedia Laboratories.
- The hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* was a gift sample provided by Kisalaya Herbal Industry, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India.
- A commercially available glycated hemoglobin kit, based on the ion exchange resin method [Coral Clinical Systems, a division of Tulip Diagnostics (P) Ltd.], was used to measure glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in whole blood samples.
- Estimation of serum lipid profiles, including total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and triglycerides (TGs), was performed using commercially available kits (Arkay Healthcare Pvt. Ltd., Surat, Gujarat, India).

2.2 High-fat diet (HFD)^{13,14}

Composition of High Fat Diet

High fat diet		Normal rat chow diet	
Nutrients	% per 100g	Nutrients	% per 100g
Carbohydrates	43	Carbohydrates	48.8
Protein	17	Protein	21
Fat	40	Fat	3
Ingredients	g per 100g	Calcium	0.8
Soya Chunks	68	Phosphorous	0.4
Vegetable Oil	6.0	Fiber	5
Ghee	6.0	Moisture	13
Milk Powder	20	Ash	8
Total Energy (Kcal/100g)	414	Total Energy (Kcal/100g)	306.2

2.3 Animals: Adult Wistar rats (180–300 g) of both sexes were used. All experiments were conducted in accordance with CPCSEA guidelines and were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of Channabasweshwar Pharmacy College (Degree), Latur, Maharashtra (Reg. No. 731/PO/Re/S/2002/CPCSEA).

2.4 Phytochemical Screening: The hydroalcoholic extract was subjected to qualitative phytochemical tests to detect the presence of major secondary metabolites. Standard chemical reagents were used for the identification of flavonoids, phenols, and tannins. Flavonoids were confirmed using lead acetate and concentrated sulfuric acid tests. Phenols were detected by iodine solution and potassium dichromate reaction. Tannins were identified using lead subacetate and bromine water. These tests followed standard protocols described in phytochemical screening manuals^{15,16}.

2.5 Acute Toxicity Study: Following OECD-425 guidelines, the extract was non-toxic up to 2000 mg/kg. Hence, test doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg were selected for efficacy studies.

2.6 Alloxan-Induced Diabetes Mellitus: Alloxan-induced diabetes is a widely recognized experimental model for studying insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (Type 1 diabetes). The diabetogenic action of alloxan begins with its preferential uptake by pancreatic β -cells via the GLUT2 glucose transporter, due to its structural similarity to glucose¹⁷ (Lenzen, 2008). Once inside the β -cells, alloxan undergoes redox cycling in the presence of intracellular reducing agents such as reduced glutathione, cysteine, ascorbate, and protein-bound sulfhydryl groups. This redox reaction leads to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), particularly hydrogen peroxide and superoxide radicals, which contribute significantly to β -cell damage¹⁸. One major mechanism of β -cell impairment involves alloxan's interaction with the sulfhydryl groups in the sugar-binding site of glucokinase—an essential enzyme for glucose sensing in β -cells. This interaction results in the formation of disulfide bonds, leading to irreversible inactivation of glucokinase and impaired glucose metabolism¹⁷.

In addition, alloxan-induced oxidative stress causes DNA fragmentation in β -cells, leading to the activation of the DNA repair enzyme poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP). Excessive activation of PARP consumes cellular NAD⁺, ultimately resulting in energy depletion and cell death¹⁹. This DNA damage and repair mechanism is a key contributor to β -cell apoptosis. Another critical pathway involves membrane depolarization of β -cells due to alloxan exposure, which leads to the opening of voltage-dependent calcium channels. The subsequent influx of calcium ions, when combined with ROS-mediated stress, triggers calcium-dependent endonucleases and other apoptotic pathways, culminating in β -cell destruction²⁰. Collectively, these events—oxidative stress, glucokinase inactivation, DNA damage, and calcium overload—converge to destroy pancreatic β -cells, severely impairing insulin secretion and causing persistent hyperglycemia.

Experimental Design: The experimental animals were randomly divided into five groups. All groups, except the normal control, were fed their respective diets prior to alloxan administration. Diabetes was induced in overnight-fasted rats by a single intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection of alloxan at a dose of 120 mg/kg body weight. Seventy-two hours post-injection, animals with fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels greater than 200 mg/dL were considered diabetic and included in the study.

The animals were allocated into the following five groups:

1. **Normal Control (NC):** Non-diabetic rats, received standard chow.
2. **Diabetic Control (DC):** Diabetic rats without treatment.
3. **Dapagliflozin Group (DAPA):** Diabetic rats treated with dapagliflozin (5 mg/kg).
4. **Combination Group I (DAPA + GE200):** Diabetic rats treated with dapagliflozin (5 mg/kg) + garlic extract (200 mg/kg).
5. **Combination Group II (DAPA + GE400):** Diabetic rats treated with dapagliflozin (5 mg/kg) + garlic extract (400 mg/kg).

All treatments were administered once daily in the morning via oral intubation prior to feeding. The treatment period lasted for 14 consecutive days. Blood glucose levels were measured using a semi-automatic analyzer based on the glucose oxidase–peroxidase method **on the first day of treatment, and subsequently on days 7, 14, 21, and 28**. At the end of the study, animals were fasted overnight and anaesthetized using light ether. The therapeutic outcomes were compared with the standard anti-diabetic drug, dapagliflozin.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of *Allium sativum*: The hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium*

sativum was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis to confirm the presence of secondary metabolites. The preliminary phytochemical screening of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* revealed the presence of several important bioactive constituents. Flavonoids were confirmed by positive reactions in the lead acetate and H₂SO₄ tests. Phenolic compounds were strongly indicated by the iodine and potassium dichromate tests. Tannins were also detected, as evidenced by positive results in the 10% NaOH, bromine water, and lead sub acetate tests. These findings collectively confirm that the garlic extract contains significant levels of flavonoids, phenols, and tannins (table 3.1 and 3.2), which may contribute to its reported antioxidant, antimicrobial, and therapeutic properties.

Table 3.1: Phytochemical Tests for Flavonoids and Phenolic Compounds

Sr. No.	Tests for Flavonoids			Test for Phenolic Compounds		
	Test Name	Observation	Result	Test Name	Observation	Result
1	Lead acetate test	Yellow precipitate	Positive (+)	Iodine test	Transient red colour	Positive (++)
2	Ferric chloride test	Dark colour	Negative (-)	Ferric chloride test	Brown colour	Negative (-)
3	H ₂ SO ₄ test	Orange colour	Positive (++)	Potassium dichromate test	Dark colour	Positive (+++)

Figure 3.1: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of *A. Sativum* on Fasting Blood Glucose Level in Diabetic Rats

3.2 Acute Toxicity Study: The hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* (HAEAS) was found to be non-toxic up to 2000 mg/kg body weight in mice via oral administration. No mortality or observable signs of toxicity were recorded. Hence, doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg were selected for further studies.

Table 3.2: Phytochemical Tests for Tannins

Sr. No.	Test Name	Observation	Result
1	Braymer's test	Dark colour	Negative (-)
2	10% NaOH test	Emulsion formation	Positive (+)
3	Bromine water test	Decolouration of bromine	Positive (++)
4	Lead sub acetate test	Creamy gelatinous ppt	Positive (+++)

Figure 3.2: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of *A. Sativum* on glycosylated haemoglobin percentage (HbA1C%) in alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus rats on 28th day

3.3 Antidiabetic Activity: The effect of Dapagliflozin alone and in combination with hydroalcoholic extracts of *Allium sativum* (HAEAS) on fasting blood glucose levels (FBG) in diabetic rats was evaluated over a period of 28 days (table 3.3 and figure 3.1). The diabetic control group maintained significantly elevated FBG levels throughout the study period, with values remaining above 340 mg/dL. In contrast, the normal control group exhibited stable and significantly lower FBG levels ($p < 0.001$) across all days. Treatment with Dapagliflozin alone (5 mg/kg) resulted in a gradual and significant ($p < 0.001$) reduction in FBG levels

from day 7 onwards, reaching 103.34 ± 1.499 mg/dL by day 28. The combination therapy of HAEAS with Dapagliflozin showed a more pronounced glucose-lowering effect. The group treated with **HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin** showed a significant reduction to 91.5 ± 1.311 mg/dL on day 28, while the group treated with **HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin** achieved the greatest reduction to 83.34 ± 0.955 mg/dL ($***p < 0.001$). Initial fasting glucose values (Day 0) were slightly variable, with some groups (e.g., Dapagliflozin and HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin) showing non-significant differences (ns), which normalized during the course of treatment.

Table 3.3: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of *A. Sativum* on Fasting Blood Glucose Level in Diabetic Rats

Fasting Blood Glucose Level (mg/dL)					
Treatment	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
Normal Control	93±1.367***	82.34±1.667** *	88.34±1.309***	91.17±1.377***	93.67±1.995***
Diabetic Control	362.84±8.507	337.34±12.759	355.5±7.145	345.67±5.755	343.5±6.742
Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	344.17±7.902ns	255.5±4.952** *	152±1.694***	130.5±2.013***	103.34±1.499** *
HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	320.34±9.546* *	238±5.86***	119.67±1.146** *	108.17±1.302** *	91.5±1.311***
HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	341.34±7.201ns	210.67±6.01** *	121.67±1.146** *	102±1.95***	83.34±0.955***

All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=6. All data are subjected to One way ANOVA followed by Dunnett 't' test. Control compare with Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, and HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg treated group *P>0.05, **P>0.01, ***P>0.001, NS; Not Significant

Figure 3.3: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of *A. Sativum* on Lipid Profile in alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus rats on 28th day

On Day 28, the evaluation of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels revealed significant differences among the experimental groups, highlighting the efficacy of the treatment regimens (table 3.4 and figure 3.2). The diabetic control group exhibited a markedly elevated HbA1c level of $15.04 \pm 0.121\%$, indicative of persistent hyperglycemia and poor glycemic control. In contrast, the normal control group maintained a significantly lower HbA1c level of $5.3 \pm 0.074\%$ ($***p < 0.001$), consistent with normoglycemic status. Treatment with dapagliflozin alone (5 mg/kg) significantly reduced HbA1c levels to $8.37 \pm 0.225\%$ ($***p < 0.001$) compared to the diabetic control, demonstrating its glucose-lowering potential. Notably, the combination therapy groups exhibited more pronounced effects. Co-administration of dapagliflozin with the hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* (HAEAS) at 200 mg/kg further reduced HbA1c to $7.3 \pm 0.124\%$, while the higher dose combination (HAEAS 400 mg/kg + dapagliflozin 5 mg/kg) resulted in a substantial reduction to $5.12 \pm 0.084\%$, closely approximating the normal control values. These findings suggest near-complete normalization of long-term glycemic levels in the high-dose combination group. Overall, all treatment groups showed statistically significant improvements in HbA1c levels compared to the diabetic control, underscoring the potential synergistic effect of combining *A. sativum* extract with dapagliflozin in managing chronic hyperglycemia

3.4 Lipid Profile: The lipid-modulating effects of dapagliflozin and its combination with the hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* (HAEAS) were evaluated in alloxan-induced diabetic rats after

28 days of treatment (table 3.5 and figure 3.3). The diabetic control group exhibited marked dyslipidemia, as evidenced by significantly elevated levels of triglycerides (208.34 ± 4.311 mg/dL) and total cholesterol (281 ± 1.694 mg/dL), along with a substantial reduction in high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels (24.5 ± 0.886 mg/dL), indicating severe impairment of lipid metabolism. In contrast, the normal control group maintained a healthy lipid profile with lower triglycerides (96.67 ± 1.499 mg/dL) and total cholesterol (138.34 ± 0.989 mg/dL), and significantly higher HDL-C levels (74.84 ± 1.078 mg/dL) ($***p < 0.001$). Treatment with dapagliflozin alone (5 mg/kg) significantly improved lipid parameters compared to the diabetic control group, reducing triglycerides to 134.17 ± 2.857 mg/dL and total cholesterol to 153.67 ± 3.888 mg/dL, while increasing HDL-C to 39 ± 0.731 mg/dL ($***p < 0.001$). Notably, combination therapy with HAEAS (200 mg/kg) and dapagliflozin demonstrated further improvements, with triglycerides at 133.17 ± 4.75 mg/dL, total cholesterol at 141.17 ± 3.764 mg/dL, and HDL-C elevated to 52.67 ± 0.761 mg/dL. The most significant therapeutic benefit was observed in the group treated with HAEAS 400 mg/kg in combination with dapagliflozin, which resulted in triglycerides being lowered to 107.5 ± 3.686 mg/dL, total cholesterol to 133.67 ± 2.895 mg/dL, and HDL-C levels rising markedly to 66 ± 1.126 mg/dL. These findings suggest a synergistic lipid-lowering effect of garlic extract when used in conjunction with dapagliflozin, highlighting its potential as a beneficial adjuvant in the management of diabetic dyslipidemia.

Table 3.4: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of A. Sativum on glycosylated haemoglobin percentage (HbA1C%) in alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus rats on 28th day

Treatment	Glycosylated haemoglobin percentage (HbA1C%)
Normal Control	$5.3 \pm 0.074^{***}$
Diabetic Control	15.04 ± 0.121
Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	$8.37 \pm 0.225^{***}$
HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	$7.3 \pm 0.124^{***}$
HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	$5.12 \pm 0.084^{***}$

All values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=6. All data are subjected to One way ANOVA followed by Dunnet 't' test. Control compare with Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, and HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg treated group *P>0.05, **P>0.01, ***P>0.001, NS; Not Significant

Table 3.5: Effect of SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin and hydroalcoholic extracts of *A. Sativum* on Lipid Profile in alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus rats on 28th day

Treatment	Lipid Profile (mg/dL)		
	Triglyceride	Total Cholesterol	HDL-C
Normal Control	96.67 \pm 1.499****	138.34 \pm 0.989****	74.84 \pm 1.078****
Diabetic Control	208.34 \pm 4.311	281 \pm 1.694	24.5 \pm 0.886
Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	134.17 \pm 2.857****	153.67 \pm 3.888****	39 \pm 0.731****
HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	133.17 \pm 4.75****	141.17 \pm 3.764****	52.67 \pm 0.761****
HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg	107.5 \pm 3.686****	133.67 \pm 2.895****	66 \pm 1.126****

All values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=6. All data are subjected to One way ANOVA followed by Dunnet 't' test. Control compare with Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, HAEAS 200 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg, and HAEAS 400 mg/kg + Dapagliflozin 5mg/kg treated group *P>0.05, **P>0.01, ***P>0.001, NS; Not Significant

4. DISCUSSION

This study highlights the enhanced antidiabetic and lipid-lowering potential of combining the SGLT2 inhibitor dapagliflozin with the hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* (HAEAS) in a high-fat diet and alloxan-induced diabetic rat model. The combination therapy led to significant improvements in key biochemical markers, including fasting blood glucose (FBG), glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and lipid profiles, when compared to monotherapy. While dapagliflozin alone effectively reduced FBG levels through its glucuretic action in the renal proximal tubules³, the co-administration of *A. sativum* extract—particularly at a dose of 400 mg/kg—resulted in a more pronounced and dose-dependent glucose-lowering effect. By the end of the 28-day treatment period, fasting glucose levels in the combination therapy groups closely approximated those of the normal control group, suggesting enhanced glycemic regulation. This improved efficacy is attributed to the bioactive phytoconstituents of garlic, such as allicin and S-allyl cysteine, known for their antioxidant properties, insulin-sensitizing effects, and pancreatic β -cell protection¹⁵.

The significant reduction in HbA1c further underscores the long-term glycemic benefits of the combination treatment. In particular, the group receiving 400 mg/kg HAEAS exhibited HbA1c levels even lower than those of the normal control, indicating a strong synergistic effect between dapagliflozin and garlic in maintaining glucose homeostasis. Beyond glycemic control, the combination regimen demonstrated marked improvements in lipid profiles, including reductions in triglycerides and total cholesterol, as well as elevated HDL-C levels—indicators of reduced cardiovascular risk^{5,15,19}. While dapagliflozin alone showed moderate improvement in lipid parameters, the addition of *A. sativum* led to near normalization, likely due to its role in modulating lipid metabolism and countering oxidative stress-induced lipid peroxidation¹⁵.

Importantly, no signs of toxicity were observed in any treatment group, confirming the safety of *A. sativum* as an adjunct therapy. These findings reinforce the therapeutic potential of integrating phytotherapeutic agents with standard antidiabetic drugs to target multiple pathological mechanisms—including hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, oxidative stress,

and dyslipidemia—offering a holistic approach to diabetes management^{10,15,20}. Further molecular studies and clinical trials are essential to confirm these findings and guide effective translation to human application.

5. Conclusion

The present study highlights the significant antidiabetic and hypolipidemic effects of combining the SGLT2 inhibitor Dapagliflozin with the hydroalcoholic extract of *Allium sativum* in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The combination therapy not only improved fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels but also favorably modulated the lipid profile, offering comprehensive metabolic control. The dose-dependent enhancement observed with the 400 mg/kg extract suggests a synergistic interaction between the phytoconstituents of garlic and Dapagliflozin. These findings support the integration of phytotherapeutic agents with conventional antidiabetic drugs to achieve improved therapeutic outcomes. However, further studies, including mechanistic and clinical investigations, are warranted to validate and translate these results into clinical practice.

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HOW TO CITE: Shivakumar Ladde, Jangme Diksha C, Giram Padmaja S, Patne Anamika S, Synergistic Antidiabetic Effects of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Allium sativum* and SGLT2 Inhibitor Dapagliflozin in Alloxan-Induced Diabetic Rats, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 1643-1652. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19546463>

